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SICILIAN NATURALISTIC NEWS:

22 *Dilophus bispinosus*; 23 *Leptometopa latipes*; 24 *Syntormon mikii*;
25 *Morophaga morella*.

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Key words: Diptera Bibionidae; Diptera Milichiidae; Diptera Dolichopodidae; Lepidoptera Tineidae; new record.

22) *Dilophus bispinosus* (Lundstrom, 1903) (Diptera Bibionidae)

Source: Facebook group Ditteri italiani <https://www.facebook.com/groups/Ditteri/permalink/4404609876329862/>

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 ♂ (housed in collection of Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorgi Tondi – Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 11.II.2023

Records validated by Paul L. T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species had not been previously reported from Sicily. This is the first record.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>; <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Dilophus bispinosus

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23) *Leptometopa latipes* (Meigen, 1830) (Diptera Milichiidae)

Source: Facebook group Ditteri italiani <https://www.facebook.com/groups/Ditteri/permalink/4383800608410789/>

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 ♀ (housed in collection of Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: River Mazzaro - Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 5.II.2023

Records validated by Paul L. T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species had not been previously reported from Sicily. This is the first record after the discovery of this species in the Coffin of Frederick II in Palermo, considering that the emperor died in Castel Fiorentino (near Foggia), on December 13, 1250. The body was taken to Palermo and placed in a sarcophagus in the cathedral.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>; <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Leptomeltopona latipes, Collection Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht, 5.II.2023 (Photo A. Ditta)

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24) *Syntormon mikii* (Strobl, 1899) (Diptera Dolichopodidae)

Source: Facebook group Ditteri italiani <https://www.facebook.com/groups/Ditteri/permalink/4395725400551643/>

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 ♂ (housed in collection of Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorgi Tondi – Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 5.II.2023

Records validated by Paul Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species had not been previously reported before from Sicily.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>; <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Syntormon mikii, Collection Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht (Photo N. Lombardo)

25) *Morphaga morella* (Duponchel, 1838) (Lepidoptera Tineidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 (housed in collection of Fabio Lo Valvo)

Site location: Serra Mannarazze (Agrigento)

Date of observation: 16.VII.2022

Records validated: Lucio Morin

Reasons of interest: This is the first record from Sicily. In Europe this species is known from the Italian mainland and from all Mediterranean countries and from Ukraine (BONELLI *et al.*, 2021).

References:

BONELLI D., SCALERCIO S. & BONACCI C., 2021. First comprehensive contribution to the knowledge of the lepidopteran fauna of Gioia Tauro Plain, South Italy (Lepidoptera). *J. Ent. Acarol. Res.*, 53 (2). <https://doi.org/10.4081/jear.2021.9632>

Resource link: <http://www.fauna-eu.org>; <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist>; <http://www.lepiforum.org>;

Genitali di *Morphaga morella*

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